

**FORMATION OF NEW CREATIVE DIRECTIONS IN MODERN FINE
ART OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the formation of new creative directions in modern fine art in the 21st century, the processes of mastering the modern principles of painting by artists, and the processes of the development of new directions in sculpture.

Keywords: fine art, sculpture, culture, artist, direction, painting, modern style, art, work, technology, international exhibition.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада XXI асрда замонавий тасвирий санъатида янги ижодий йўналишларнинг шаклланиши, рассомлар томонидан рангтасвир йўналишини замонавий тамойиларини ўзлаштириш жараёнлари, ҳайкалтарошлиқда янги йўналишларнинг ривожланиши жараёнлари ҳақида батафсил маълумот берилган.

Калит сўзлар: тасвирий санъат, ҳайкалтарошлиқ, маданият, рассом, йўналиш, рангтасвир, замонавий услуб, санъат, асар, технология, халқаро кўргазма.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о становлении новых творческих направлений в современном изобразительном искусстве в XXI веке, процессах освоения художниками современных принципов живописи, процессах развития новых направлений в скульптуре.

Ключевые слова: изобразительное искусство, скульптура, культура, художник, направление, живопись, стиль модерн, искусство, произведение, техника, международная выставка.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, in May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to

further increase the efficiency of the field of fine and applied arts” dated April 21, 2020 No. PD-4688, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures related to supporting the entrepreneurial activity and employment of young people, their social protection and meaningful organization of their free time" 20th of 2021 Decree No. PD-6208 of April. It is known that the 20th century was a period of sharp changes in the art of Uzbek music, “unconventional” compositional creativity and new forms of concerts appeared. In this regard, the concept of “variety” entered our circulation in musical culture.

At the same time, as the visual art of Uzbekistan is developing in harmony with the world artistic culture, this situation is also causing new changes in the thinking of artists. The modern works created by artists are not just excerpts from life, but are observed to be based on specific philosophical ideas. Therefore, it should be noted that today's color image of Uzbekistan, unlike the processes of fifteen or twenty years ago, is taking on a modern tone. Such works are manifested in abstract and complex artistic styles in the spirit of the avant-garde, which are difficult to perceive, regardless of the principles of the original expression of existence in the general public's understanding of fine art.

In this regard, the painter Akmal Noor's “Sleeping Angel” (2004), Lee Tatyana's “Dream from the Right” (2004), Farukh Akhmadaliev's “Caravan” (2004), and Lyudmila Sadygova's “Sunny Day” (2003) are examples. can be brought. It should be noted that the expansion of the scope of such works increases the weight of non-traditional methodological approaches in the creative process.

Since the 2000s, the mastering of modern principles in painting has advanced significantly, artists are trying to conquer the advanced trends in the field of world visual arts. From the end of the 20th century, the rapid development of technology, the processes of globalization in the world culture and art, the development of mass information and computer technologies, as well as the expansion of the scope of international exhibitions have activated a new creative way of thinking in painting, as a result of which the range of modern approaches is expanding. In this regard, the regular holding of the Tashkent International “Biennale” exhibition at the threshold of the 21st century is significant. After all, under the influence of such art exhibitions, the introduction of new artistic directions, such as installation, installation, into the visual art of Uzbekistan, is causing methodological changes in the work of many artists and sculptors. At this point, it is permissible to dwell briefly on the works of Vyacheslav Okhunov and Jamal Usmanov.

It is noteworthy that in their work, the painting type of visual art is in harmony with the plastic tools characteristic of sculpture. In this regard, examples can be given of the works of Vyacheslav Okhunov's "Forgotten Sand", "Bird's Tongue", "Thirst", "Spring", "Chess Pieces" and "Mirage" exhibited at the 2001 "Spirit and Imagination" exhibition of Jamal Usmanov.

Jamal Usmanov's creativity in this regard was especially active. His installation on Alisher Navoi's "Language of a Bird", which was shown at the exhibition and gained a lot of attention, is ideologically and formally distinguished. In this installation, the ideas expressed by Alisher Navoi are interpreted in symbolic forms. He tried to express how the forest birds, who live a normal life without compromise, made a voluntary trip to the Kaf mountain with the help of a leader and went on the road at the request of the righteous King, and the difficult trials, hardships and rites they go through in this process. In this series of works, the lush green landscape embodies the hardships of the road, where the space gradually changes based on colors and materials. Taking the blue fabric at the end of the composition as a symbol of the universe represents the image of Mount Kaf.

Jamal Usmanov's argument about the weak based on "The Language of the Bird" is also vividly revealed. The image of the weak, holding the elephant by its various parts and interpreting it in different ways through their senses, was realized through the medium of sculpture. The impressive performance of this installation is determined by the fact that the full figures illuminated by lights create a certain mysterious atmosphere. The composition can be found in music, theatre, photography, literature, and all kinds of fine arts.[4] Also, the exhibits in the exhibition named "Dedication to the Island", "Mirage", "Origin of the Spirit", "Spring", "Chess Pieces" have their own artistic solution.

With the establishment of the Art Academy of Uzbekistan in 1997, the regular holding of national and international exhibitions accelerated the process of implementing modern directions. Also, the practice of new thinking and creative application in sculpture began to become active. Sculptors began to appear who took a more serious approach to modernity than to traditional approaches. As a result of the promotion of initiative approaches by some creators, new directions have developed. In this regard, the work of Bayot Mukhtorov and his students is important. With their new creative views, they introduced the technique of working with new materials in easel sculpture and significantly increased the development status of the industry. The main criteria for

development are the figurines of the second type of local sculptors, decorative ornaments and garden sculptures [5].

The dynamic composition of the compositions of the creative group under the leadership of Bayot Mukhtorov was accompanied by a strong rhythm. The human figure, which was addressed as the main goal until now, has a secondary place in their work, and thematic compositions have risen to a priority level. The new approach they formed was evident in the creation of colorful composite works by attaching multi-material elements to the basic image, unlike traditional sculpture. Therefore, these methodological approaches initiated by them can be evaluated as a major change achieved in modern easel sculpture.[6] In 2006, the exhibition "Sculpture of Uzbekistan 1991-2006" held in the center of modern art (now in the "Tashkent Photo House") provided more accurate information on the development of modern easel sculpture. The presented works showed that along with the traditional directions in the easel sculpture, modern principles are also developing. If in the works of Anvar Rakhmatullaev, Ravshan Mirtojiev, Akhmad Shoymurodov, Tolagan Tajikhojaev, Ulugbek Mardiev, traditional realism and some free-form approaches can be observed, in the works of Kurban Norkhorozov, Azamat Khotamov, Ulash Urokov, Tolagan Tajihjojaev, Mukhtar Ablokhlov, and other artists, Eastern poetic style, as well as Marina In the works of Borodina, Saidolim Sharipov, and Bayot Mukhtorov, research typical of contemporary art can be felt. Uzbekistan has achieved a high level of creative development in the distant past.[7]

In addition to the painting type of fine art, the development of new trends in easel sculpture is noticeable. Since the late 1990s, there has been a growing emphasis on modernity over traditional approaches among sculptors. The work of Bayot Mukhtorov and his students Risdovlat Abdullaev, Zinnur Gayfullin, Akrom Toraev, Alexey Toroppov, Alexey Protopopov can be cited as an example in this regard. With their new creative views, they widely used the technique of working with new materials in easel sculpture. In addition, there are many artists who have made a significant contribution to the development of 20th century Uzbek painting. [8]

The above-mentioned art examples occupy a worthy place in the development of modern visual art of Uzbekistan, and today, in the training of artists, it is called to develop a sense of attitude to advanced artistic directions. The student inspires in the hearts of young people the desire to discover new directions and styles. After all, the future personnel of the field should not only master the professional skills related to the theory of colors and shades in the educational

process, but also develop creative-artistic thinking based on memory, and seek to develop innovative approaches to creating works. For example, usually in the process of training, the basics and methods of painting are taught, and the skill of expressing existence in its own way is formed. Although this is enough to give students a decent experience in the realistic style, it is difficult to say that it is enough to satisfy the need related to the education of an independent artist who expresses advanced ideological views. For this purpose, it seems appropriate to pay special attention to the issues of creating an artistic work in independent work or group classes in order to master fine arts on the above basis. This situation ensures that national personnel can create their own creative field in their independent activities after artistic education.

Significant changes are occurring in the visual art of Uzbekistan, which is developing in harmony with the world artistic culture in the current age of modern techniques and technologies. In particular, the increasing availability of large-scale (electronic) image recording equipment through computer technology is changing the role of visual art as a medium for mass promotion and advertising. Also, public events, public holidays and modern city street decoration are increasing the need for skilled computer graphics creators and designers. This further strengthens the responsibility of training the personnel being trained in higher educational institutions and vocational colleges, where there is fine and practical art education.

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